

Composition of Kapok Seeds.

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Eriodendron anfractoeum DC seeds were collected in September 1923 and 1925 from Java, Sumatra and the Malaya State Settlements. These were stored in tin cans after drying and were properly sealed. Within three months these were pulverised. Their oils were extracted for 28 hours with petroleum ether in Soxhlet apparatus. Various values of the oils were quantitatively determined, in triplicate, by the same procedure as used by Griffing and Alsberg (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1931, 23, 908).

The data obtained from the above stated analysis is being presented below, which seem to indicate, that a definite and uniform composition of these seeds, as assumed by the above quoted authors, is not a universal phenomena. There are many factors which may modify their composition. It not only depends on the time of collection of seeds, the manner of their storage, the age and variety of the parent plant and the character of the soil on which it is grown, but also on the geographical position where the plant may have been located. Table shows the composition of the oils extracted from kapok seeds collected from various geographical positions.

	Griffing & Alsberg.	Obtained by the author.		
		Java.	Sumatra.	Malaya States.
Specific gravity at 25°	0·9225	0·9105	0·9215	0·9387
Refractive index	1·4691	1·4691	1·3810	1·5081
Saponification value	191·6	170·8	179·2	198·1
Iodine number (Hanus)	94·1	96·3	95·7	91·3
Acid value	9·65	Not	determined	
Saturated acids (%)	17·15	18·90	17·85	19·60
Unsaturated acids (%)	76·32	75·98	76·56	75·00

This work was done while the author was in charge of the Biological Laboratories, Saint Marys, Kansas, U. S. A.

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